

Сімех Корнелія Юріївна,

старший викладач Ужгородського торговельно-економічного інституту

Державного торговельно-економічного університету
e-mail: info@utei-knteu.org.ua

Яртим Артем Васильович,

магістрант кафедри менеджменту, підприємництва та торгівлі Ужгородського торговельно-економічного інституту Державного торговельно-економічного університету

e-mail: info@utei-knteu.org.ua

Data about the authors

Petro Havrylko,

Ph.D. of Economics, Professor, Director of the Uzhhorod Institute of Trade and Economics of the State University of Trade and Economics

e-mail: info@utei-knteu.org.ua

Cornelia Simekh,

Senior Lecturer of the Uzhhorod Institute of Trade and Economics of the State University of Trade and Economics
e-mail: info@utei-knteu.org.ua

Artem Yartym,

Master's student of the Department of Management, Entrepreneurship and Trade of the Uzhhorod Institute of Trade and Economics of the State University of Trade and Economics

e-mail: info@utei-knteu.org.ua

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RUSINA Yu. O.

Financial planning as a basis for management of the company's financial activities

The subject of the research is the relationship between financial planning and financial activities of an enterprise through elements, principles, tools and decision-making mechanisms in the field of finance and their impact on the management of financial activities of an enterprise.

The aim of the research is to define financial planning as the basis for managing the financial activities of an enterprise through the study of its main elements, principles and tools.

Research methods. The following general scientific methods were used in writing the article: analysis and synthesis, which allowed to consider financial planning as a system, identify structural elements and interrelationships; induction and deduction, which helped to summarize individual facts and formulate general laws of financial planning; abstraction and generalization, which contributed to the formation of the theoretical foundations of financial planning and the identification of key principles and tools for its use in the management of financial activities of an enterprise; classification and systematisation of financial planning.

Results of the investigation. It has been determined that financial planning is a key element of managing the financial activities of an enterprise, as it ensures efficient allocation of resources, forecasting of income and expenses, and minimisation of financial risks. It is determined that the process of financial planning includes the development of short-term and long-term financial plans, which allows the enterprise to adapt to changes in the external environment, ensure financial stability and increase profitability. It is determined that one of the main functions of financial planning is to identify sources of financing and optimise their use to achieve the strategic and tactical goals of the enterprise, which involves analysing financial flows, assessing the investment attractiveness of projects and managing working capital. It is proved that effective financial planning allows an enterprise to reduce costs, optimise the tax burden and increase competitiveness in the market. It has been established that an important aspect of financial planning is the forecasting of possible financial risks and the development of mechanisms to minimise them, which may include diversification of funding sources, risk insurance, and the use of modern methods of financial analysis and control.

Scope of the results. Enterprise finance, financial planning, budgeting, investment, financial activity of the enterprise.

Conclusions. The study has determined that financial planning is a prerequisite for effective enterprise management, as it allows controlling financial resources and contributing to the achievement of strategic

goals, increasing profitability, and ensuring financial stability of the enterprise. It has been determined that the use of modern financial planning tools contributes to improving the efficiency of enterprise, its adaptability to market changes and long-term sustainability in a competitive environment. A synergistic combination of elements, principles and planning tools is proposed that will allow the enterprise to adapt to changes in the market environment, optimise financial flows and increase competitiveness.

Keywords: financial planning, management, finance, enterprises, financial activity, budgeting, elements, principles, tools, efficiency.

РУСІНА Ю. О.

Фінансове планування як основа управління фінансовою діяльністю підприємства

Предметом дослідження є взаємозв'язок фінансового планування з фінансовою діяльністю підприємства через елементи, принципи, інструменти та механізми прийняття рішень у сфері фінансів та їх вплив на управління фінансовою діяльністю підприємства.

Метою дослідження є визначення фінансового планування як основи управління фінансовою діяльністю підприємства через дослідження основних його елементів, принципів та інструментів.

Методи дослідження. При написанні статті було використано такі загальнонаукові методи: аналіз і синтез, які дозволили розглянути фінансове планування як систему, виявити структурні елементи та взаємозв'язки; індукція і дедукція, що допомогло узагальнити окремі факти та сформулювати загальні закономірності фінансового планування; абстрагування і узагальнення, які сприяли формуванню теоретичних основ фінансового планування та визначенню ключових принципів та інструментів його використання в управлінні фінансовою діяльністю підприємством; класифікація і систематизація, що дозволило впорядкувати елементи, принципи та інструменти фінансового планування, таблично-графічний та ін.

Результати роботи. Визначено, що фінансове планування є ключовим елементом управління фінансовою діяльністю підприємства, оскільки забезпечує ефективний розподіл ресурсів, прогнозування доходів і витрат, а також мінімізацію фінансових ризиків. Встановлено, що процес фінансового планування включає розробку короткострокових і довгострокових фінансових планів, що дозволяє підприємству адаптуватися до змін у зовнішньому середовищі, забезпечувати фінансову стійкість та підвищувати рентабельність. Визначено, що однією з основних функцій фінансового планування є визначення джерел фінансування та оптимізація їх використання для досягнення стратегічних і тактичних цілей підприємства, що передбачає аналіз фінансових потоків, оцінку інвестиційної привабливості проектів та управління оборотним капіталом. Доведено, що ефективне фінансове планування дозволяє підприємству знижувати витрати, оптимізувати податкове навантаження та підвищувати конкурентоспроможність на ринку. Встановлено, що важливим аспектом фінансового планування є прогнозування можливих фінансових ризиків і розробка механізмів їхньої мінімізації, що може включати диверсифікацію джерел фінансування, страхування ризиків, застосування сучасних методів фінансового аналізу та контролю.

Галузь застосування результатів. Фінанси підприємств, фінансове планування, бюджетування, інвестування, фінансова діяльність підприємства.

Висновки. В результаті дослідження визначено, що фінансове планування є необхідною умовою ефективного управління підприємством, оскільки дозволяє контролювати фінансові ресурси та сприяти досягненню стратегічних цілей, підвищенню прибутковості, забезпеченню фінансової стабільності підприємства. Встановлено, що використання сучасних інструментів фінансового планування сприяє підвищенню ефективності діяльності підприємства, його адаптивності до змін ринку та довгостроковій стійкості в конкурентному середовищі. Запропоновано синергічне поєднання елементів, принципів та інструментів планування, що нададуть змогу підприємству адаптуватися до змін у ринковому середовищі, оптимізувати фінансові потоки та підвищити конкурентоспроможність.

Ключові слова: фінансове планування, управління, фінанси, підприємства, фінансова діяльність, бюджетування, елементи, принципи, інструменти, ефективність.

Formulation of the problem. In an unstable economic environment, high competition and rapid changes in the state's financial policy, the issue of effective management of financial activities of enterprises is of particular relevance. The basis of such management is financial planning, which ensures the rational allocation of resources, control over financial flows and minimisation of risks. Despite the obvious importance of financial planning, in practice many companies face problems with its implementation and effective use. The main problems include: low level of financial forecasting; insufficient attention to strategic planning; inefficient financial management structure; influence of external factors; limited access to financial resources. Thus, the need to improve financial planning as a key tool for managing the financial activities of enterprises is an urgent scientific and practical problem, the solution of which will help to increase the financial stability of enterprises, optimise their costs and achieve strategic goals.

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. Financial planning is an important tool for managing the company's finances, which allows ensuring its financial stability, increasing the efficiency of resource use and minimising financial risks. In scientific publications and studies, this problem is considered from different points of view, which indicates its relevance and multidimensionality. V. Bratiuk and S. Nesterova in their work [3] defined the processes of planning and financial control, where they analysed the planning factors, the focus of planning types, categories of financial control, ratings of the scale of impact and risk probabilities. T. Hrynychuk, A. Tsikhanovska, and D. Chychkaliuk [6], found that financial planning plays a key role in the system of planning the activities of an enterprise, ensuring the economic feasibility and effectiveness of the measures developed to achieve its strategic goals and objectives. The authors substantiate the methods used in the process of financial planning, namely: calculation and analytical, regulatory, balance sheet, optimisation of planning decisions, economic and mathematical modelling, network, and software and targeted. The authors proposed a generalised methodology of financial planning, which is relevant in the changing conditions of the market economy of our country. K. Blyzniuk in his work [2] summarised the aspects of budgeting at enterprises and analysed the

information on the practical aspect of implementing the budgeting method in the activities of enterprises, identified the factors that affect the results of such a management decision.

O. Shulha [21] revealed the role and importance of financial planning of enterprise activity in ensuring its financial stability. The author noted that financial planning significantly reduces the uncertainty of the market environment and its negative consequences for the business entity, and highlighted areas for improving the organisation of financial planning of the enterprise (budgeting as an instrument of operational controlling; financial controlling; strategic planning at the enterprise; risk minimisation; reduction of accounts receivable). L. Dokiienko [6] studied the current global trends in financial planning and analysis at an enterprise, identified the differences between domestic and international practice of building a financial planning process at an enterprise and proposed stages and principles of building an effective process of financial planning and analysis at an enterprise, taking into account the best international practices.

B. Zasadnyi and A. Tkachenko [10] identified the factors influencing the budgeting system as a leading link in the financial planning of enterprise business processes. They considered the issues of the planning system and the basic principles of the enterprise, analysed the criteria for assessing the financial condition of the enterprise, its sustainability and competitiveness. The authors analysed the options for increasing the efficiency of the budgeting system in the financial planning of business processes of an enterprise, identified ways to improve and prospects for the future development of the budgeting process at an enterprise. Another group of authors, N. Vyhovska, A. Polchanov, V. Dovhaliuk and O. Polchanov [5], studied the financial planning of IT enterprises, where they concluded that business planning reflects its ability to manage available resources, taking into account opportunities and risks, with a miscalculation of various scenarios. A. Nechyporenko and S. Stabias [15] paid attention to the study and generalisation of theoretical aspects of financial planning and forecasting in the enterprise management system, considered the main approaches to the interpretation of the essence of the concept of 'financial planning', and identified the elements of financial planning in an enterprise. The authors reveal the role

of financial planning and forecasting in the enterprise management system. O. Kalchenko, O. Shyshkina, and V. Danylovykh [11] analysed the impact of digitalisation on the system of financial planning and budgeting of modern enterprises, identifying the main reasons for the lack of high-quality financial planning in domestic business entities. The authors identified the advantages and disadvantages of digitalisation processes in the financial and economic activities of enterprises, the tasks and possibilities of automating financial planning and budgeting processes, analysed the essence, main characteristics and features of domestic and foreign software products used by business entities in budgeting and financial planning.

D. Dema, L. Sus and Yu. Sus [7] proposed a mechanism for organising financial planning at enterprises, where, based on the stages of financial planning, three main subsystems of activity planning (strategic, current and operational planning of financial activity) are characterised. M. Maksimova and A. Shcherbyna [14] substantiated the conceptual provisions of financial planning of enterprises, summarised the main positive effects of the implementation of financial planning. O. Andrus and N. Berezova [1] studied the financial planning of an enterprise as a tool for managing the results of an enterprise's activities in competitive market conditions, which allows to weigh the available financial resources and sources of their receipt to solve the outlined tasks, justify the distribution of funds to the budget, extra-budgetary funds, banks and other creditors, distribute and use the enterprise's profit and ensure the balance of planned expenses and income of the enterprise on the principles of self-sufficiency and self-financing.

V. Tyshchenko [19] clarified the concept of «financial planning», identified the stages of the financial planning process at the enterprise and grouped the main methods of financial planning. Y. Velykyi and O. Chvartatska in their work [4] defined the content and place of financial planning in the enterprise management system, summarised the semantic features of the definition of «financial planning», characterised the types, forms and methods of financial planning that form the theoretical basis of the planning process in the practical activities of domestic enterprises. O. Lisnichuk and M. Berezan [13] analysed the systematic relationship of planning components, its structural elements, which

ensure a high level of financial performance. The authors summarised the directions of improvement of financial planning and their factors that can have a positive impact on the activities of an industrial enterprise. Despite the in-depth study of this issue, financial planning, precisely in the context of the basis of managing the financial activities of an enterprise through a synergistic combination of elements, principles, and tools, requires further research, which became the purpose of the research.

Presenting main material. In modern business conditions, characterised by high dynamics of the market environment, instability of economic processes and competition, an enterprise should pay special attention to planning financial flows to ensure stability and development. Financial planning is a key tool for managing the financial activities of an enterprise, as it ensures the efficient allocation of financial resources, control over income and expenses, and the formation of a financial strategy to achieve long-term goals [1–5]. Financial planning allows forecasting future financial performance, assessing risks, developing measures to minimise them, and ensuring the optimal capital structure of the enterprise, which covers the strategic, tactical and operational levels, allowing the enterprise to align its long-term interests with current financial capabilities. Effective financial planning helps to increase profitability, ensure solvency, optimise costs and enhance the company's investment attractiveness. Thus, financial planning is an integral part of the overall enterprise management system and determines its competitiveness in the market [6–9]. Financial planning is the process of developing and substantiating the goals, directions and methods of using the company's financial resources to achieve its strategic and tactical objectives, which involves estimating future income and expenses, analysing financial flows, identifying sources of funding and optimising the allocation of resources [4–11].

The main goal of financial planning is to ensure the financial stability of the enterprise, its solvency, profitability and efficient use of capital. Financial planning plays an important role in the functioning of an enterprise (Fig. 1) [3–8]. The main elements of financial planning include several key stages. The first of them is the analysis of the financial condition of the enterprise, which involves the study of the structure of assets and liabilities, assessment of financial stability, liquidity and profitability, as well

Fig. 1. The role of financial planning in managing the financial activities of an enterprise

Source: built by the author with the use of [3–11].

as cash flow analysis [12–16]. The next stage is the formation of financial goals and strategy, which includes the definition of short-term and long-term financial goals and the development of a financial strategy for the enterprise. This is followed by the development of financial plans and budgets, which includes current financial planning, such as operating budgets and cash flow forecasts, tactical planning, which includes the income and expense budget and the capital investment budget, and strategic planning, which defines the financial strategy for 3–5 years.

An important element is revenue and expense forecasting, which involves market analysis, sales forecasts and an assessment of changes in costs. Optimisation of financial resources includes planning sources of funding, both equity and debt, as well as controlling costs and profitability. The final stage is the control and adjustment of financial plans, which includes monitoring the implementation of financial plans, identifying deviations and adjusting the strategy in accordance with changes in the external and internal environment of the enterprise [Table 1] [14–19].

Table 1. Key elements of financial planning

Element	Components
Analysis of the financial condition of the company	1. Study of the structure of assets and liabilities. 2. Assessment of financial stability, liquidity and profitability. 3. Analysis of cash flows.
Formation of financial goals and strategy	1. Determination of short-term and long-term financial goals. 2. Development of the financial strategy of the enterprise.
Development of financial plans and budgets	1. Current financial planning (operating budgets, cash flow forecasts). 2. Tactical planning (income and expense budget, capital investment budget). 3. Strategic planning (financial strategy for 3–5 years).
Forecasting of income and expenses	1. Market analysis and sales forecast. 2. Assessment of changes in costs.
Optimisation of financial resources	1. Planning of funding sources (own and borrowed capital). 2. Cost and profitability control.
Control and adjustment of financial plans	1. Monitoring the implementation of financial plans. 2. Identifying deviations and adjusting the strategy.

Source: compiled by the author based on [14–21].

The key principles of financial planning (Table 2) include the principle of target orientation, which means that financial planning should be focused on achieving both strategic and tactical goals of the enterprise [11–17]. The principle of target orientation includes profit growth, market expansion, cost optimisation, increased investment attractiveness, etc. The principle of comprehensiveness is also important, as it stipulates that financial planning should cover all aspects of the company's financial activities. This applies not only to income and expenses, but also to investments, lending, tax liabilities, cash flow management and other financial indicators that affect the overall state of the company. Another important principle is the principle of continuity, which means that financial planning should be carried out on an ongoing basis, enabling the company to quickly adapt to changes in the market environment, anticipate possible financial risks and effectively manage financial flows. At the same time, the principle of flexibility is in place, which allows for prompt adjustment of financial plans in response to changes in the internal and external environment. For example, changes in tax legislation, exchange rates, raw material prices, or product demand may require immediate adjustments to the financial strategy [16–21].

For the efficient allocation of financial resources, the optimality principle is applied, according to which financial resources should be allocated in such a way as to ensure maximum efficiency of capital use. This implies optimising costs, increas-

ing profitability and achieving financial stability of the enterprise. The principle of validity is also important, which means that financial planning should be based on real data, forecasts, financial calculations, risk analysis and the use of modern methods. Without accurate analysis and sound financial calculations, effective planning is impossible. The last but not least is the principle of balancing risks and returns. Any financial decision should take into account possible risks and their impact on the financial position of the company. The pursuit of high profitability is always accompanied by certain risks, so the task of financial management is to find a balance between possible risks and expected returns to ensure financial stability and development of the enterprise [14–19]. Thus, adherence to the principles of financial planning allows an enterprise to effectively plan its financial resources, achieve strategic goals and ensure stable operation in a dynamic market environment (Table 2).

Financial planning tools are important mechanisms that allow a company to effectively manage its financial resources, assess risks, optimise costs and ensure financial stability. One of the key tools is budgeting, which involves the process of preparing and controlling the company's budget, which allows to determine future financial needs, control expenses and income. The main types of budgets include the operating budget, which covers the income and expenses of the main activity, the financial budget, which contains plans for managing assets, capital and liabilities, and the cash budget,

Table 2. Principles of financial planning in the context of managing financial activities of an enterprise

Principles	Characteristics.
The principle of targeting	Financial planning should be focused on achieving the strategic and tactical goals of the company (profit growth, market expansion, cost optimisation, etc.).
The principle of comprehensiveness	The planning covers all financial aspects of the company's activities: income, expenses, investments, loans, tax liabilities, etc.
The principle of continuity	Financial planning should be done on an ongoing basis to ensure adaptation to changes in the market environment and financial conditions.
The principle of flexibility	The plan should be able to adapt quickly to changes in the internal and external environment, such as changes in tax legislation, exchange rates or product demand.
The principle of optimality	Financial resources should be allocated in such a way as to maximise the efficiency of capital use.
The principle of reasonableness	Planning should be based on realistic data, forecasts, financial calculations, risk analysis and the use of modern techniques.
The principle of balancing risks and returns	Financial decisions should take into account potential risks and their impact on the company's financial position.

Source: compiled by the author on the basis of [11–21].

which forecasts cash flow and allows the company to avoid cash gaps [6–14].

The next important tool is financial analysis, which includes methods for assessing the financial position of an enterprise. The main methods include liquidity analysis, which determines the company’s ability to meet short-term obligations, profitability analysis, which assesses the efficiency of asset and capital use, and solvency analysis, which helps to assess the company’s ability to meet long-term financial obligations. Financial analysis helps to identify problems in a timely manner and make informed management decisions. An important aspect of financial planning is forecasting financial indicators, which involves estimating future revenues, expenses, investments and financial risks. For this purpose, statistical methods and econometric models are used to build the most accurate forecast of the company’s financial position. Forecasting allows a company to prepare for possible changes in market conditions and effectively manage its resources. Another important tool is investment planning, which involves the evaluation and selection of investment projects. It is based on an analysis of profitability, payback periods, and risk levels, which allows the company to decide whether it is appropriate to invest in certain assets or projects. Investment planning helps to expand production capacity, introduce new technologies, and increase the company’s competitiveness [4–8].

A separate role is played by cash flow management, which ensures control over cash inflows and

outflows, allowing the company to maintain the required level of liquidity and solvency, as well as to avoid cash shortages or surpluses. Effective cash flow management allows optimising the use of financial resources, reducing risks and ensuring financial stability [11–16]. Also important is capital investment planning, which determines the needs of the enterprise in fixed assets, their renewal and sources of financing of capital investments, which allows the enterprise to maintain an adequate level of material and technical base, which contributes to increased productivity and production efficiency. Another key financial planning tool is the optimisation of the capital structure, including the choice between equity and debt, which is necessary to minimise financial risks and maximise the company’s profitability. The optimal ratio of equity and debt allows a company to maintain financial stability and ensure the required level of investment activity. The last but not least important financial planning tool is tax planning, which determines the best ways to minimise the tax burden in accordance with the current legislation. Tax planning allows an enterprise to use tax benefits efficiently and avoid unnecessary tax expenditures, which contributes to its financial efficiency [2–9]. Thus, financial planning tools (Table 3) play a key role in ensuring the stable development of an enterprise, helping it to allocate resources efficiently, reduce financial risks and achieve strategic goals.

Therefore, financial planning is a key element of managing a company’s financial activities, which helps

Table 3. Financial planning tools in managing the financial activities of an enterprise

Tools	Feature.
Budgeting	The process of preparing and controlling the company’s budget allows you to determine future financial needs, control expenses and income. The main types of budgets are: operating budget; financial budget; cash budget – forecasts cash flow.
Financial analysis	Methods of analysing the financial condition of an enterprise include: liquidity analysis; profitability analysis; solvency analysis.
Forecasting financial indicators	It involves estimating future income, expenses, investments and financial risks based on statistical methods and econometric models.
Investment planning	Evaluation and selection of investment projects based on the analysis of profitability, payback periods and risk level.
Cash flow management	Ensures control over cash inflows and outflows to maintain liquidity and solvency of the company.
Capital investment planning	Determines the needs for fixed assets, their renewal and sources of financing for capital investments.
Optimisation of capital structure	Includes the choice between equity and debt capital to minimise financial risks and maximise profitability.
Tax planning	Determines the best ways to minimise the tax burden in accordance with the current legislation.

Source: compiled by the author based on [4–16].

to ensure its financial stability, profitability and efficient use of resources. The synergistic combination of elements, principles and planning tools helps an enterprise to adapt to changes in the market environment, optimise financial flows and increase competitiveness.

Conclusions

Financial planning is a key element of managing a company's financial activities, as it ensures efficient allocation of resources, forecasting of income and expenses, and minimisation of financial risks. The process of financial planning includes the development of short-term and long-term financial plans, which allows an enterprise to adapt to changes in the external environment, ensure financial stability and increase profitability. It is established that one of the main functions of financial planning is to identify sources of financing and optimise their use to achieve the strategic and tactical goals of the enterprise, which involves analysing financial flows, assessing the investment attractiveness of projects and managing working capital. It is proved that effective financial planning allows an enterprise to reduce costs, optimise the tax burden and increase competitiveness in the market. It is established that an important aspect of financial planning is the forecasting of possible financial risks and the development of mechanisms to minimise them, which may include diversification of funding sources, risk insurance, and the use of modern methods of financial analysis and control.

Therefore, because of the research, it has been determined financial planning is a prerequisite for effective enterprise management, as it allows controlling financial resources and contributing to the achievement of strategic goals, increase profitability, and ensure financial stability of the enterprise. It has been determined that the use of modern financial planning and management tools contributes to improving the efficiency of enterprise, its adaptability to market changes and long-term sustainability in a competitive environment. A synergistic combination of elements, principles and planning tools is proposed, which will allow the enterprise to adapt to changes in the market environment, optimise financial flows and increase competitiveness.

References:

1. Andrus, O. I., Berezova, N. V. (2014). Analiz tsilei, zavadan, pryntsyypiv ta metodiv finansovoho planuvan-

nia yak instrumentu upravlinnia rezultatamy diialnos-ti pidpryiemstva [Analysis of goals, objectives, principles and methods of financial planning as a tool for managing the results of enterprise activity]. *Efektivna ekonomika = Ekonomika effektivnist*, 4, URL: nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/efek_2014_4_72 [in Ukrainian].

2. Blyzniuk, K. O. (2023). Biudzhetuвання zovnishnoekonomichnykh vytrat yak skladova finansovoho planuvannya na pidpryiemstvi [Budgeting of foreign economic costs as a component of financial planning at the enterprise]. *Efektivna ekonomika = Effective Economy*, 8, URL: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/efek_2023_8_39 [in Ukrainian].

3. Bratiuk, V. P., Nesterova, S. V. (2024). Rol planuvannya ta finansovyi kontrol v zabezpechenni diialnosti pidpryiemstva [The role of planning and financial control in ensuring the activities of the enterprise]. *Efektivna ekonomika = Effective Economics*, 4, URL: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/efek_2024_4_39 [in Ukrainian].

4. Velykyi, Yu. M., Chvartatska, O. V. (2018). Teoretychni osnovy finansovoho planuvannya ta prohozuvannya na pidpryiemstvi [Theoretical foundations of financial planning and forecasting at the enterprise]. *Efektivna ekonomika = Effective Economics*, 11, URL: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/efek_2018_11_3 [in Ukrainian].

5. Vyhovska, N. H., Polchanov, Yu., Dovhaliuk, V. V., Polchanov, O. Yu. (2022). Finansove planuvannya diialnosti pidpryiemstv sfery IT [Financial planning of the activities of IT enterprises]. *Efektivna ekonomika = Effective Economics*, 12, URL: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/efek_2022_12_9 [in Ukrainian].

6. Hrynchuk, T. P., Tsikhanovska, A. M., Chychkaliuk, D. O. (2021). Udoshkonalennia metodyk finansovoho planuvannya v systemi finansovoi bezpeky pidpryiemstva [Improving financial planning methods in the system of financial security of the enterprise]. *Pryazovskyi ekonomichnyi visnyk = Priazovsky Economic Bulletin*, 1, P. 73–77 [in Ukrainian].

7. Dema, D. I., Sus, L. V., Sus, Yu. Yu. (2021). Formuvannya mekhanizmu finansovoho planuvannya na pidpryiemstvi v umovakh nevyznachenosti ta nestabilnosti zovnishnoho seredovysshcha [Formation of the mechanism of financial planning at the enterprise in conditions of uncertainty and instability of the external environment]. *Biznes Inform = Business Inform*, 9, P. 207–215 [in Ukrainian].

8. Dokiienko, L. M. (2021). Finansove planuvannya ta analiz na pidpryiemstvi: suchasni hlobalni trendy ta perspektyvy rozvytku [Financial planning and analysis at the enterprise: modern global trends and prospects for development]. *Pidpryiemnytstvo ta innovatsii = Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 16, P. 51–58 [in Ukrainian].

9. Yepifanova, I. Yu., Bezruchenko, I. V., Palamarchuk, N. O. (2016). Finansove planuvannya diialnosti vitchyznianskykh pidpriemstv za pokaznykamy rentabelnosti [Financial planning of domestic enterprises by profitability indicators]. *Ekonomichnyi analiz = Economic analysis*, 23, 2, P. 45–50 [in Ukrainian].

10. Zasadnyi, B. A., Tkachenko, A. V. (2021). Systema biudzhetuвання yak providna lanka finansovoho planuvannya biznes–protsesiv pidpriemstva [Budgeting system as a leading link in financial planning of business processes of an enterprise]. *Naukovyi visnyk Uzhhorodskoho natsionalnoho universytetu. Seria : Mizhnarodni ekonomichni vidnosyny ta svitove hospodarstvo = Scientific Bulletin of Uzhhorod National University. Series: International economic relations and the world economy*, 35, P. 33–37 [in Ukrainian].

11. Kalchenko, O., Shyshkina, O., Danylovykh, V. (2022). Problemy udoskonalennia protsesiv avtomatyzatsii finansovoho planuvannya na pidpriemstvakh [Problems of improving the processes of automation of financial planning at enterprises]. *Problemy i perspektyvy ekonomiky ta upravlinnia = Problems and prospects of economy and management*, 1, P. 88–95 [in Ukrainian].

12. Lapina, I., Yanchev, A. (2016). Sutnist, problemy ta perspektyvy finansovoho planuvannya pidpriemstv v suchasnykh umovakh [The essence, problems and prospects of financial planning of enterprises in modern conditions]. *Naukovyi visnyk Odeskoho natsionalnoho ekonomichnoho universytetu = Scientific Bulletin Odesa National Economic University*, 10, P. 73–86 [in Ukrainian].

13. Lisnichuk, O. A., Berezan, M. V. (2020). Osnovni skladovi potochnoho finansovoho planuvannya na pidpriemstvi [The main components of current financial planning at the enterprise]. *Zbirnyk naukovykh prats Universytetu derzhavnoi fiskalnoi sluzhby Ukrainy = Collection of scientific works of the University of the State Fiscal Service of Ukraine*, 1–2, P. 208–221 [in Ukrainian].

14. Maksimova, M. V., Shcherbyna, A. I. (2019). Kontseptualni polozhennia finansovoho planuvannya na pidpriemstvi [Conceptual provisions of financial planning at the enterprise]. *Efektivna ekonomika = Effective Economy*, 7, URL: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/efek_2019_7_29 [in Ukrainian].

15. Nechyporenko, A. V., Stabias, S. M. (2022). Finansove planuvannya ta prohnozuvannya v systemi upravlinnia pidpriemstvom [Financial planning and forecasting in the enterprise management system]. *Efektivna ekonomika = Effective Economics*, 10, URL: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/efek_2022_10_19 [in Ukrainian].

16. Proskurovych, O. V., Horbatiuk, K. V., Valkov, O. B., Valkova, O. O. (2019). Modeliuvannya systemy finansovoho

planuvannya pidpriemstva [Modelling the system of financial planning of an enterprise]. *Visnyk Khmelnytskoho natsionalnoho universytetu. Ekonomichni nauky = Bulletin of Khmelnytsky National University. Economic Sciences*, 6(1), P. 146–150 [in Ukrainian].

17. Rubakha, M., Halaiko, A. (2016). Teoretychni aspekty doslidzhennia finansovoho planuvannya na pidpriemstvi [Theoretical aspects of the study of financial planning at the enterprise]. *Naukovyi visnyk Odeskoho natsionalnoho ekonomichnoho universytetu = Scientific Bulletin Odesa National Economic University*, 5, P. 143–156 [in Ukrainian].

18. Smochko, V. Yu. (2020). Udoshkonalennia orhanizatsiino–upravlinskykh aspektiv finansovoho planuvannya na pidpriemstvi [Improving the organisational and managerial aspects of financial planning at the enterprise]. *Formuvannya rynkovykh vidnosyn v Ukraini = Formation of market relations in Ukraine*, 2, P. 117–122 [in Ukrainian].

19. Tyshchenko, V. V. (2017). Vprovadzhennia finansovoho planuvannya na pidpriemstvi [Implementation of financial planning at the enterprise]. *Naukovyi visnyk Uzhhorodskoho natsionalnoho universytetu. Seria : Mizhnarodni ekonomichni vidnosyny ta svitove hospodarstvo = Scientific Bulletin of Uzhhorod National University. Series: International economic relations and world economy*, 6(2), P. 125–129 [in Ukrainian].

20. Titenko, Z. M., Shnaider, A. V. (2021). Rol finansovoho planuvannya ta prohnozuvannya u zabezpechenni finansovoi stikosti pidpriemstva [The role of financial planning and forecasting in ensuring the financial stability of the enterprise]. *Formuvannya rynkovykh vidnosyn v Ukraini = Formation of market relations in Ukraine*, 9, P. 113–119 [in Ukrainian].

21. Shulha, O. A. (2023). Napriamy udoshkonalennia orhanizatsii finansovoho planuvannya diialnosti pidpriemstva [Directions for improving the organisation of financial planning of enterprise activities]. *Pidpriemnytstvo ta innovatsii = Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 26, P. 58–62 [in Ukrainian].

Data about the author

Yuliia Rusina,

Associate Professor of the Department of Finance and Business Consulting, Kyiv National University of Technologies and Design, Ph.D. in Economics, Associate Professor
e-mail: [rusinaulia80@gmail.com](mailto:rulinaulia80@gmail.com)

Дані про автора

Русіна Юлія Олександрівна,

доцент кафедри фінансів та бізнес–консалтингу, Київський національний університет технологій та дизайну, к.е.н., доцент
e-mail: [rusinaulia80@gmail.com](mailto:rulinaulia80@gmail.com)